

A new cold-tolerant cultivar for Tripura

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In Tripura, rice is harvested in Oct or Nov and fields remain fallow until transplanting starts in Feb. Three rice crops are not easily grown on the same land because temperature varies from 5 to 15°C during fallow and farmers have no suitable cold-tolerant variety.

We have used three cold-tolerant parents from IRRI to develop varieties with cold tolerance at early growth stages.

Table 1. Criteria for scoring for cold tolerance.

Score	At early seedling stage	Seedling vigor or seedling height (cm)
1	All germinated, none died	Above 10
3	Less than 30% died	8-10
5	30 to 50% died	5-7
7	Over 50% died	3-4
9	100% died	Less than 1

Table 2. Cold tolerance and seedling vigor of selected varieties at early seedling stage.

Index no.	IR no.	Cross	Total strains	Strains (no.) with given score									
				At early seedling stage					For seedling vigor				
				1	3	5	7	9	1	3	5	7	9
TRC245	IR26216	Thimpu/IR5853-118-5//KN-1B	23	1	12	3	6	1	1	3	8	10	1
TRC246	IR26226	Thimpu/IR9129-102-2//KN-1B	34	1	23	6	4	0	2	3	12	17	0
TRC247	IR26237	Toyonishiki/IR9093-195-1//KN-1B	4	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	0

The crosses were evaluated and selected during boro. In 1981, 61 promising fixed strains were selected. Five-day-old germinated seeds of the strains were subjected to cold treatment in the refrigerator at 4°C for 10 d using the method outlined by T. G. Li and B. S. Vergara. They were scored for cold tolerance and seedling vigor 10 d after removal from the refrigerator (Table 1).

Sixty-eight percent of the entries had less than 30% seedling death and moderate seedling vigor (5-10 cm high) after cold treatment (Table 2). The same cultures were field evaluated in 1981-82 boro for flowering duration, plant height, number of tillers, panicle length, and single-plant weight. Five promising entries – C-10, C-14, C-13, C-9, and C-23 – were selected for further evaluation.

They were planted in mid-Nov 1982 in a replicated randomized design with Kalinga, a cold-tolerant culture of the region, as control. C-10 yielded better than the other test varieties and the control (Table 3).

C-10 is a cross of the Bhutan variety Thimpu, with IR9129-102-2, which was then crossed with KN-1B. It is a photo-period-insensitive semidwarf that matures in 140-145 d. C-10 has good early seedling vigor, moderate tillering ability, highly synchronized flowering, late leaf senescence, fully exerted and compact panicles, and high fertility. Average yield is 6.5 t/ha. Insect and disease incidence was negligible.

This promising culture has been proposed for a minikit test program in Tripura. □

Table 3. Performance of promising cold tolerant varieties, Tripura, India.

Character	C-10	Kalinga (control)
Days to heading	117	117
Days to maturity	145	148
Plant height (cm)	85	82
Tillers/plant	10	11
Plant type	Semidwarf	Semidwarf
Leaf senescence	Late	Medium
Panicle length (cm)	28	20
Filled grains/panicle	223	87
Fertility (%)	93	84
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.44	26.15
Yield/m ² (g)	720	520
Yield (t/ha)	6.5	4.50
Awneless or awnless	Awnless	Awnless
Kernel length (mm)	7.72	7.94
Kernel width (mm)	2.94	2.71
Length-breadth ratio	2.62	2.92
Grain shape	Medium	Medium
Grain husk color	Light yellow	Straw
Endosperm color	Waxy white	Light brown

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Breeding for salt-tolerant rice strains

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Various studies have identified Jhona 349 (Pakistan) as relatively salt tolerant and Magnolia (USA) as salt sensitive. The two

cultivars were crossed and the resulting F₁ and F₂ were grown under saline conditions. P57, with relative salt tolerance, was selected in F₃, from which seven relatively salt-tolerant progeny were isolated in F₄. The progeny were tested at various salinity levels for 5 years (1976-80) in artificially salinized 6 x 6 x

1 m field basins with drainage systems (Table 1).

We conducted a microyield trial in 1981 to test those strains against standard salt-tolerant strains Damodar, Getu, and Giza 159 (from Egypt). The first two were developed in India by pureline selection from local germplasm. The field was

artificially salinized (pH 8.7, ECe 5.2 dS/m, SAR 44.6, ESP 39.6, TSS 42.6, Ca^{++} + Mg^{++} 5.5, and Na^+ 71.6 meq/liter. Arti-

ficial salinity was developed by adding a 1:4:5:10 of magnesium sulfate, sodium chloride, calcium chloride, and sodium

sulfate — salts usually present in saline soils of Pakistan. The crop was irrigated from a tubewell with saline sodic water containing HCO_3^- meq/liter, TSS 35 meq/liter (Ca^{++} + Mg^{++} 4.8, Na^+ 30.2) with a SAR of 19.5. Net plot size per entry was 4 m². Hills of one seedling each were spaced at 23 x 23 cm in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

NR74-108 yielded significantly more than the other strains, including Damodar and Getu (Table 2). NR74-108 is a semi-tall rice with stiff straw and medium-long grain that does not shatter. It flowers in 121 d. It may be suitable for cultivation on marginal saline soils and may be used as a donor of salt tolerance genes. □

Table 1. Response of plant progenies to salinity^a (percent reduction over control^b).

Cultivar	Florets/ panicle	Panicle fertility (%)	Yield per plant (g/m ²)
NR74-79	15 g	9 g	42 h
NR74-92	38 ab	20 b	70 b
NR74-93	33 cd	13 ef	61 c
NR74-96	36 bc	16 cd	65 d
NR74-97	30 d	15 de	67 cd
NR74-106	37 b	18 bc	54 f
NR74-108	18 f	13 f	49 g
Jhona 349 (resistant parent)	25 e	20 b	68 bc
Magnolia (susceptible parent)	40 a	30 a	80 a

^apH 8.7, ECe 7.2 dS/m at 25°C, SAR 59.7, ESP 44.3. ^bpH 7.7, ECe 2.3 dS/m at 25°C, SAR 8.4, ESP 12.0. Figures followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of significance.

Table 2. Performance of salt-tolerant rice strains in saline fields.^a

Cultivar	Yield g/m ²	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/ plant	Panicles/m ²	Days to flowering	Panicle length (cm)	Florets/ panicle	Panicle fertility (%)	1000- grain wt (g)
NR74-108	34 a	101 b	10 cd	228 e	121 c	25 ab	109 d	89 a	23 ab
NR74-79	32 b	111 a	11 bc	252 d	125 b	27 a	135 b	84 bc	23 a
Damodar	28 c	93 d	14 a	333 b	120 c	20 cde	127 c	86 ab	15 d
Giza 159	21 d	74 e	12 ab	285 c	117 d	22 bc	133 b	81 d	19 c
Getu	27 e	92 d	13 a	341 a	152 a	21 cd	151 a	82 cd	16 d
Jhona 349	28 f	96 c	8 de	204 f	114 e	18 de	105 e	83 bcd	23 a
Magnolia	17 g	96 c	7 e	184 g	103 f	17 e	103 e	67 e	22 b

^aFigures followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level.

PBN1, a semidwarf upland rice cultivar tolerant of iron deficiency

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PBN1 (Prabhavati) is a semidwarf (75 cm) recommended for cultivation in iron-deficient black soils (calcareous vertisols with 40-65% montmorillonitic clay and pH 8.0-9.2) in Maharashtra State. It is an induced mutant of the tall local cultivar Ambemohor obtained through ethyl methanesulfonate (0.2%) seed treatment.

PBN1 is nitrogen-responsive and is suitable for direct seeding in uplands. It tolerates iron chlorosis and has dark green foliage. Its roots have more efficient iron-

Performance of PBN1 under direct seeding in UVT on irrigated black soils.

Cultivar	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)				Days to maturity	Lodging score ^b
	1980	1981	1982	Weighted mean		
PBN1	2.5	3.1	4.1	3.3	119	0
PBN4	1.7	2.4	3.1	2.5	117	1
PBN7	2.1	2.6	3.3	2.8	116	0
PBN20	1.5	2.6	2.8	2.4	119	1
PBN30	2.3	2.5	3.3	2.7	115	3
Ambemohor (local)	2.3	2.4	3.4	2.8	116	4
Jalgaon 5	2.3	2.9	3.2	2.9	116	4
Tuljapur 1	2.6	2.5	3.0	2.7	113	4
SE ±	0.21	0.26	0.34	.24		
CD (0.05)	0.64	0.81	0.97	.73		

^aAv of 3 sites. ^bBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

reductive capacity than high yielding semidwarfs with Dee-geo-woo-gen in their parentage. Maturity ranges from 115 to 120 days, which helps it fit well in the rice — wheat, rice — legume, or rice — oil-seed double-cropping sequence in the

canal command areas. Grain is medium coarse, translucent, and scented.

PBN1 was evaluated under direct seeding in uniform variety trials (irrigated black soils) at three sites for three seasons (see table). It yielded 20% more than the